

A TORCHBEARER FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

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"If one man can destroy everything, why can't one girl change it?"

— Malala Yousafzai, *I Am Malala: The Story of the Girl Who Stood Up for Education Who Shot by Taliban.*

When the Taliban controlled Swat Valley, Pakistan, one girl spoke out, refused to be silent and fought for the right to an education.

She fought with words when they fought with guns.

She spoke for education when they spread ignorance.

She stared death in the face and walked away.

She changed the world....

Showing in many ways Malala is simply an ordinary girl. Yet, thrown into extraordinary circumstances she had the bravery to continue to speak out and campaign for education and equality, making her a truly inspirational person.

Malala her name, borrowed from a legendary Pashtun warrior who has been referred to as Afghanistan's Joan of Arc." This name that Ziauddin chose for his daughter also helped inspire her to fight for others. Research paper topic is to consider include a study about famous women in history like the Pashtun warrior or Joan of Arc and the differences they made in history or how they can serve to inspire future girls. Written as an autobiography Malala talks of her life as an early child, the Taliban occupation and being shot, all the way through to her 16th Birthday when she addressed the UN assembly. She herself is a true story of love, loss and tremendous courage, showing how a single voice can change the world.

A remarkable life inspiring autobiographical book 'I am Malala', She wrote this hoping that her message would reach people around the world so they would understand that how difficult the education for millions of children in the world. In the words of Malala, "When I was born, people in our village commiserated with my mother and nobody congratulated my father. I arrived at dawn as the last star blinked out. We Pashtuns see this as an auspicious sign. My father didn't have any money for hospital or for a midwife so a neighbour helped at my birth. My parents' first child was stillborn but I popped out kicking and screaming. I was a girl in a land where rifles are fired in celebration of a son, while daughters are hidden away behind a curtain, their role in life simply to prepare food and give birth to children." (1) Story of Malala's life begins here but this was face of her community not of her family so her story of gaining education also begins here. Malala considered her father a Falcon, for her who made her free to do what she wanted as she visualized to touch the peak of highest mountain. Malala belonged that maternal side where her great grandmother fought against kabilaayi tribal clan in order to make her nine year old

son free from their clutch. Malala expected same from her mother who was illiterate although opt influenced by her own daughter's campaign. Malala's life journey explains the first step of success that was environment of her house and great co-operation of parents to inbuilt a kid's world of gaining making courage by their own.

This very youngest Nobel Laureate girl stamps before the world through UNO what decades before Vivekanand enlightened the whole world by his speech in Chicago uttering "We are responsible for what we are whatever we wish ourselves to be, we have the power to make ourselves. The goal of mankind is knowledge inherent in man. No knowledge comes from outside: it is all inside. Just like Swami Vivekanand she started speech in UNO before Nobel committee and other members addressing them "My dear brothers and sister paid gratitude for selecting her for Nobel prize as well as expressed thanks for unconditional love of her parents. The gist of Malala's speech awakens all of us from cozy sleep in our cocoon. Some words are mesmerizing glimpse in the below paragraph.....

"Being living in the Swat valley in Pakistan under Taliban rule I had only two options, one was to remain silent and wait to be killed and second was to speak up and then to be killed. I chose the second one. I decided to speak up tell my story, not because it is unique, but because it is not. It is the story of many girls. I am those 66 million girls who are out of school. People ask me why education is important especially for girls. My answer is always same, what I have learnt from the first two chapters of the Holy Quran, is the word Iqra, which means read and the word, nun wal-qalam means 'by the pen.' And therefore as I said last year at the United Nations, "One child, one teacher, one pen and one book can change the world." In this rapid success and modernization millions still suffer from the very old problems of hunger, poverty, injustice and conflicts. Why I dedicate the Nobel prize money to the Malala Fund, to help give girls everywhere a quality education and call on leaders to help girls like me. My great hope is that this will be the last time we must fight for the education of our children. We want everyone to unite to support us in our campaign so that we can solve this once and for all." (2)

Malala is enrolled at the University of Oxford, where she is studying Philosophy, Politics and Economics at Lady Margaret Hall. She balances her school work and social life leading with the fights for girls. HE NAMED ME MALALA in October 2015 award winning documentary movie acclaimed audience in 175 countries and in 11 languages. She spent her 19th birthday in 2016 with refuse girls living in Dadaab and Kakuma camps in Kenya and Mahama camps in Rwanda. She opened a secondary school for Syrian refuse girls in Lebanon's Bekka Valley on her 18th birthday, she travelled to Nigeria on her 17th birthday to meet with the families of the victims and add her voice to the outcry demanding for their safe return and 16th birthday was a hallmark in UNO. That's education what she is spreading message of upbringing kids with a pious motif in life for others what she has decided to make a benchmark on her every birth day. Education starts from self, she has become benchmark of self-objective. UNESCO Malala Fund for Girls' Right to Education. Part of the "Better Life, Better Future" Global Partnership for Girls' and Women's Education, the fund was established in 2012 to expand girls' access to quality and gender-

responsive education and ensure safe learning environments, especially in countries affected by conflict and disaster. The Islamic Republic of Pakistan initially committed 10 million USD to the Fund, and since 2014 the CJ Group is another major contributor to the Fund, along with other supporters. Cambodia, Egypt, Nepal, Pakistan, Tanzania, Vietnam, Nigeria and some more countries are under the umbrella of fund to get benefitted to ensure quality learning and quality life.

There is no better champion for girls' education than Malala Yousufzai, who survived a Taliban assassination attempt for championing the cause." (3) Tim Cook, CEO of Apple also joined hands with courageous Malala to advocate education equality. He demonstrates her as the most influential woman in present time, and feels honored to help her extend the important work she is doing to empower girls around the world. "Ask social scientists how to end global poverty, and they will tell you: Educate girls. Capture them in that fleeting window between the ages of 10 and 14, give them an education, and watch a community change: Per capita income goes up, infant mortality goes down, the rate of economic growth increases, the rate of HIV/AIDS infection falls. Child marriage becomes less common, as does child labor. Educated mothers tend to educate their children." (4)

She absorbs her father's ideals and develops with her own impressive intelligence, courage, talent and determination. Her qualities together in uncommon fashion. Her advocacy on behalf of girls' education and women's right is crystal clear. When Taliban threats finally shut down her school, she tells journalists that They cannot stop her. She will get her education if it's at home, school or somewhere else. This is "modest strategy" a young woman is feted globally. Malala blogged for BBC under a pseudonym when she was just 11. She gave interviews to print, radio and TV journalists. Desmond Tutu nominated her for the International Children's Peace Prize. *The New York Times* produced a documentary on her advocacy prior to the attempt on her life. It is this high media profile that brought Malala to the near-fatal attention of the Taliban. Her rise to celebrity in Pakistan, through her outspoken advocacy and her father's agency, is a strong thread in the book, but she presents it almost with a shrug. In an interview with American news network CNN, she expressed her hope to become Pakistani prime minister so she can expend maximum budget on education.

I want to end my views on Malala by her own words that we realize the importance of our voice when we are silent. There are two powers in the world, one is sword, other is pen but the third power is stronger than both that is woman.

Reference

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4. Marie Arana, book review 'I am Malala' October 11, 2013